

ORIGINAL RESEARCH

The relationship between trade openness, financial development and economic growth: Evidence from Generalized method of moments

Robeena Bibi¹, Sumaira^{2*}

¹School of Public Administration, Hohai University, Nanjing China

¹Department of Management Sciences, Islamia College University Peshawar, Pakistan

Correspondence Muhammad Naveed Sumaira

Corresponding Author:
sumairakhan321321@gmail.com

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Abstract

This study examines the effect of trade openness and financial development on economic growth four South Asian countries for the period of 1980-2017 using static and dynamic models. The results indicates that stock market development positively effect economic growth. The results validate that all three proxies of stock market perform a significant and positive role in augmenting economic growth in the sample countries. Trade openness, inflation and real interest rate significantly reduce economic growth while saving rise economic growth. The findings of this study have important policy implication for the sample countries regarding rising stock market in order to strengthen economic growth.

Keywords: Trade Openness, Stocks Market development, Difference GMM, System GMM

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1.Introduction

The previous literature on trade openness and financial development and its relationship with economic growth indicates that a developed and well-operative economy requires a sound financial system which have strong financial regulations and institutional framework which efficiently allocate savings into investments. Likewise, international trade openness is also been considered that its plays a very important role in rising economic growth. The composition of financial institutions, financial markets, pension funds, securities markets and other intermediaries as well the regulatory institutions that allows the flow of money to accelerate economic activities is termed as financial system. The improvement of financial

services poised of the establishments and development of financial institutions, and markets that upkeep investment and growth process ((FitzGerald, 2006). Therefore, it is agreed that a well-established financial structure is a crucial driver of economic progression which should be integrated to developmental policies. A well-established financial structure which is composed of better financial markets help ease savings into investments. It's also strengthening financial activities which in-turn increase the supply of financial facilities and enhance the growth level. According to (Patrick, 1966) countries trying to achieve self-sustained growth of their economies and for this purpose they are trying to develop their financial sector Patrick (1966).